

“METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR STUDYING THE HISTORY OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS”

Iroda Rasulovna Tishabayeva

Ferghana State Technical University Associate Professor of the

Department of Social Sciences and Sports

Email: tishabayevairodahon@gmail.com.

ORCID: 0009-0001-3081-8917

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17966793>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 15th December 2025

Accepted: 16th December 2025

Online: 17th December 2025

KEYWORDS

preschool education, methodology, comparative analysis, source studies, archival documents, micro-historical analysis, historiography.

ABSTRACT

This article provides a scholarly and theoretical analysis of the methodological foundations for studying the history of preschool education institutions in Uzbekistan. The research employs key methodological approaches such as historicism, comparative-analytical analysis, systemic inquiry, source studies, and interdisciplinary integration. These methods enable an in-depth examination of the causes and consequences of transformations that occurred in the preschool education system between 1946 and 1991, as well as their connection with socio-economic conditions and state policy.

In the years of independence, the comprehensive, in-depth, and objective study of Uzbekistan’s history, as well as its interpretation based on scientifically grounded evidence, has been recognized as one of the priority directions. Historical sources, archaeological findings, and written monuments indicate that the social, political, and cultural transformations that occurred in the territory of Central Asia have long constituted an important component of world civilization. The history of our homeland is an integral part of global history and is distinguished not only by its millennia-old antiquity but also by its enduring and complex historical processes that have significantly contributed to the development of human civilization. This underscores the necessity of studying historical truth on a scientific basis, supporting it with evidence, and interpreting it impartially.

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. M. Mirziyoyev, has emphasized: “Every nation glorifies its own history. But nowhere else is there such a rich history and such great ancestors as ours. Anyone who comes to this center should gain a full understanding of our history and leave with great spiritual enrichment” [10.] This indicates that historiography is not only the study of the past but also a vital instrument for strengthening national pride, patriotism, and historical memory in the consciousness of future generations. Therefore, historians bear great responsibility, as historical knowledge plays an important role in nurturing a highly educated, patriotic, and broad-minded young generation.

This research analyzes the formation and development of the preschool education system in Uzbekistan within a historical and cultural context. The study examines the

activities of preschool institutions during the period from 1946 to 1991, considering them in close connection with the political, social, economic, and cultural conditions of that era.

In the course of the study, not only were the activities, material and technical base, and personnel policy of kindergartens and nurseries explored, but also the socio-economic circumstances of the period and the influence of state policy were taken into account. Archival documents, periodical press materials, government resolutions, the scholarly works of pedagogical researchers, as well as the practical experience of preschool institution leaders and teachers who worked during the period under study, served as key sources for the historical analysis.

During the examination of the history of preschool education institutions in Uzbekistan from 1946 to 1991, the fundamental concepts relevant to the research topic were first identified. Definitions of such terms as “preschool education system,” “education of preschool-aged children,” “material and technical base of kindergartens,” and “educational and upbringing process in kindergartens” determine the methodological orientation of this research. The conceptual clarity of these terms contributes to the scientifically grounded analysis of the factors and levels of change throughout the research process.

In the research process, understanding the essence of the concepts “kindergarten” and “preschool education,” as well as determining the proper context in which they should be used, is of significant importance.

The word *bog'cha* has existed in the Uzbek language since ancient times and originally meant “small garden” or “green area.” [1.355.]. The root *bağ/baq* (“garden”) found in Turkic languages, combined with the diminutive suffix *-cha*, conveys meanings such as smallness, affection, or endearment. By the early twentieth century, particularly during the Soviet period, the term *bog'cha* began to be used as a direct translation of the Russian term *Детский сад* (“children’s garden”), acquiring the form *bolalar bog'chasi*, and gradually became established as a scientific and pedagogical term.

The term *preschool education (maktabgacha tarbiya)* is defined in the National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan as a specialized pedagogical process aimed at preparing children for school education. As a scientific and pedagogical concept, it originates from the notion of *Kindergarten*, introduced by the German pedagogue Fredrich Frebel (1782–1852). From the second half of the nineteenth century, this concept spread widely in European pedagogy. In Frebel’s educational system, young children were likened to flowers requiring care within a “garden,” where play, labor, and creative activities were harmoniously integrated [2.37.].

In Uzbekistan, the term *maktabgacha ta'lim* has appeared in official documents since the 1930s in the form *maktabgacha tarbiya*. By the 1940s–1950s, it was normatively defined as a distinct component of the state education system. The word *bog'cha*, meanwhile, has continued to be used in both colloquial speech and official terminology as a synonym for “preschool educational institution.”

In constructing the theoretical and methodological foundation of this research, both international and national scholarly works on historical methodology were utilized. The methodological basis of the study was enriched by the views of prominent scholars such as P. M. Bitsilli, Bolingbroke, A. Ya. Gurevich, E. M. Zhukov, I. D. Kovalchenko, A. J. Toynbee, L. Febvre, E. Freeman, and K. Jaspers. In particular, the approaches of L. Febvre and E.

Freeman—emphasizing the importance of evaluating historical events within their broader socio-cultural context and studying them in an interdisciplinary framework—played a crucial role in shaping the conceptual direction of the research [3.].

Conclusion

This section has provided a comprehensive analysis of the theoretical and methodological foundations for studying the history of the preschool education system in Uzbekistan during 1946–1991, based on the principles of historicism and interdisciplinary approaches. The research effectively employed modern conceptual frameworks of historical science, including synergetics, system analysis, comparative, retrospective, and problem-chronological methods. It was determined that the Soviet-era preschool education system was shaped under the influence of the dominant ideology, socio-economic factors, and state policy, and that the content and organizational structure of education were carried out in a centralized manner.

References:

- 1.O'zbek Tilining Izohli Lug'ati (Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language). Tashkent: "O'zbekiston Milliy Ensiklopediyasi" State Publishing House, 2022, p. 355.
- 2.Qodirova, F., & Toshpo'latova, Sh. Maktabgacha Pedagogika [Preschool Pedagogy]. Tashkent: Tafakkur, 2019, p. 37.
- 3.Bolingbroke, H. Pis'ma ob izuchenii i pol'ze istorii [Letters on the Study and Usefulness of History]. Moscow, 1978.; Freeman, E. Metody izucheniya istorii [Methods of Historical Research]. Translated from English. Moscow, 1986.; Zhukov, E. M. Ocherki metodologii istorii [Essays on the Methodology of History]. 2nd ed. Moscow, 1987, 439 p., Toynbee, A. J. Postizhenie istorii [A Study of History]. Moscow, 1991.
- 4.<https://xs.uz/uz/post/shavkat-mirziyoev-mamlakatimizdagidek-boj-tarikh-bobolarimizdek-buyuk-allomalar-hech-qaerda-joq>